

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17048981

Analysis Of Adverbial Phrases In Yorùbá Spoken Across Òyó Central Senatorial District Of Òyó State

Dr. Joseph Olábòdé Fátóba

Department of Yorùbá
Federal College of Education, Obudu, Cross River State, Nigeria
fatobajoseph7@gmail.com/+234 805 9925 102

ABSTRACT

The syntax of Yorùbá has been described and analysed several times using different linguistic parameters, but, there is yet to be an account of Yoruba adverbial phrases driven and anchored on X-bar theory. Based on this motivation, the study employed the theoretical tenets of headedness of the X-bar framework to analyse the Yorùbá adverbial phrase structures. The study aimed at describing types, forms, functions, and the applicability of X-bar theory to adverbials phrases in Yoruba sentence structure. To achieve the research objectives, the qualitative approach was adopted, and data for the research obtained from competent Yorùbá native speakers, using a check list designed to guide in the oral interview. The population of the study were all the adults in Òyó central senatorial district who are native speakers of Yorùbá language. However, the study also adopted cluster sampling method in selecting the representative for the study. The data obtained was validated, using to a large extent, the researcher's introspection, and then to some extent, the linguistic competence possessed by the informants that were appointed. For data analysis, the study first, employed Leipzig glossing rules to code the data collected, and then employed the X-bar theory, which is that theory of syntax that is concerned with phrase structure analysis, and deals specifically with intermediate categories. The results were analysed based on the aim of the study.

Keywords: X-bar theory, syntax, Yoruba adverbial phrases

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Any given language is made up of syntactic classes of words; that is, words that behave in a similar way in the sentences of the language. Such classes of words are traditionally referred to as parts of speech. A central assumption of syntax (and of grammar generally), is that, language is a set of strings of words and morphemes, that meet a set of well-formedness conditions that can be expressed into rules (Chomsky,1988, Radford 1988). Thus, syntax is an instantiation of rules, for constructing full sentences out of phrases.

Different languages are characterized by different syntactic principles. These principles make up the grammar of a language; the syntactic processes that the various elements like phrases and other constituents undergo form an important study of grammar. The principles are also part of the native speaker's linguistic knowledge. The task of the linguist often is to formulate and test hypotheses about what the principles of a language are, that is, to determine either its syntax, morphology, phonology, or in totality the grammar of a language. This means that the Linguist's hypotheses and the speaker's knowledge (intuition) interface to affirm or refute assumptions about these hypotheses. The evidence produced characterizes the grammar of the language and the basis upon which utterances of the language are understood fulfil the criteria of its descriptive adequacy. Radford (1988: 28) attests to this:

A grammar of a language is descriptively adequate if it correctly specifies which structures are (and not) syntactically, semantically, morphologically and phonologically well-formed in the language, and also properly describes the syntactic, semantic, morphological and phonological structure of the sentence in the language in such a way as to provide a principled account of the native speaker's intuition about the structure.

The work will legitimize further the search for a linguistic theory of language which is assumed to be a body of statements that capture generalizations about a particular phenomenon. The work will provide a rich linguistic literature that is current for the fulfilment of pedagogical roles and further research in Yorùbá syntax.

Sequel to the above, this work seeks to analyse Yorùbá phrases, with a view to examine and describe the adverbial phrase structure of Yorùbá, in terms of the different syntactic interactions, which the least composite units called phrases, like the noun and verb phrases undergo, to form sentences, using the X-bar model. The work further examines the different types of Yorùbá adverbial phrases, and the extent to which the theory (X-Bar) is applicable to Yoruba adverbial phrases.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The design adopted for this study is both descriptive and qualitative. The data for the research was sourced through oral interviews. The researcher also used the direct observation technique whereby competent native Yorùbá speakers were observed in natural speech settings. In the tenets of the deductive tradition, the research, being a theory driven research, has employed the X-Bar Framework for the analysis of data. The X-bar model, anchored on headedness principle tries to bring out what is common in the structure of phrases, based on the relationship between the head and its constituents. The research also used the Leipzig Glossing rules for the organization and coding of data for easy understanding of the meanings of individual words used. Here, detailed interlinear glossing is adopted for morpheme-by-morpheme correspondence. In the convention, interlinear morpheme-by-morpheme glossing makes explicit the syntactic and grammatical properties of words and parts of a word.

3.0 Types of Adverbial Phrases in Yorùbá.

An **adverbial phrase** (also known as an **adverb phrase**) is a group of words that functions as an adverb in a sentence. That is, it modifies a verb, adjective, adverb, clause, or the sentence as a whole. AdvP often feature an adverb (known as the head word) being modified by other elements, but not always. Here are types of adverbial phrases we have in Yorùbá.

3.1 Adverbial Phrase of Time

Adverb as an open word-class is heterogeneous in nature because it allows other categories to function in the same slot as adverbs. Other words which belong to different categories such as nouns can also function as adverbs in Yorùbá. Consider the list below:

alé yíí	Tonight
òru	Mid-night
òwúrò yíí	This morning
àná	Yesterday
òní	Today
òla	Tomorrow
Òsè tí ó nbò	Next week

Some of the items in the above list are further explained with their use in the following examples 1a-c:

(a) **Alé yíí** “tonight”

Tolú kò wá mó [AdvP ni **alé yíí**
 Tolú-N not-NEG. come not in-PREP night this-DEM
 ‘Tolú will not come anymore tonight’

Figure 3.1: X-Bar Schema Showing Internal structure of Adverbial Phrase of Time

(b) Òru “mid-night”

Àwọ̀n ajá máa ń gbó [AdvP ní òru]
 3-PRON dog-PL do-always PRT bark in-PREP mid-night
 ‘Dogs do bark at mid-nights’

Figure 3.2: X-Bar Schema X-Bar Schema Showing Adverbial Phrase of Time

(c) Òwúrò yíí “this morning”

Mo fẹ̀ lọ sí Makurdi [AdvP ní òwúrò yíí]
 1SG would go-FUT to Makurdi-LOC in-PREP morning this-DEM
 “I would like to go to Makurdi this morning”

Examples 1(a) *alé yíí* “tonight” and (c) *òwúrò yíí* “this morning” are both noun phrases functioning as adverbial in the sentences. “*alé*” (night) and “*òwúrò*” (morning) are heads of the phrases respectively. They were both modified by demonstrative “*yíí*”, and only nouns take such modifiers in Yorùbá. In example (b), we have prepositional phrase functioning adverbially. *ní òru* “at mid-night” is a prepositional phrase headed by a noun *òru* “mid-night” whereas morpheme /ní/ “at” introduces the preposition. These lexical items clearly maintained their lexical classes but have to change in the structure to fulfill semantic role of complements to the verbs. From this linear position, it becomes evident to conclude that they are adverbial complements of time and adverbial adjunct of time respectively.

3.2 Adverbial Phrase of Place

Adverbs of place are also known as locative adverbs in the literature (Shopen, 2007). Place or locative adverbs typically modify the verb by describing where an action occurs. They “are used to indicate where something happens or takes place” (Kirkpatrick 2007:167). Place adverbs “are typically postpositional phrases but can also be single lexical items” (Berk 1999:188). Yoruba place adverbs can also be realised in various forms, they can occur as single-words (pro-forms), and phrases. Here are some examples in Yorùbá: 2

- (a) *ibí* ‘Here’
 (b) *ibè yẹ̀n*

place	that	'Over there'
(c) ibi	gbogbo	
Where	every	'Everywhere'
(d) ibikíbi		Anywhere
(e) Níbí	yíí	
Here	this	There
(f) Níbè	yẹn	
There	that	Over there
(g) Ilé		Home
(i) Òde		Outside

The list is exemplified below in: 3

(a) *ibí* "here"

mo gbé-e sí *ibí*
 1SG carry-PST-Obj. to-PREP here
 'I placed it here'

(b) *ibè yẹn* "over there"

Şadé sùn sí *ibè yẹn*
 Şadé-N sleep-PST at-PREP there that
 'Şade slept over there'

(c) *Ibi gbogbo* "everywhere"

Ibi gbogbo ló gba alágbára
 Place where can-AUX take powerful
 'Everywhere is a home for the brave'

(d) *ibikíbi* "anywhere"

A lè lọ sí *ibikíbi* tó wù wá
 1PL may-AUX go-V to-PREP anyplace which admire us
 'We may go to anywhere we chose'

In examples 3 (a) to (d) *ibí* "here", *ibè yẹn* "over there", *ibi gbogbo* "everywhere", and *ibikíbi* "anywhere" are all locative/place adverbs which indicate locations in the sentences. Yorùbá place phrasal adverbs share similar properties with that of time adverbs. Similar to time adverbs, place adverbs can occur in the form of prepositional phrases. This is done by combining NP with PP /sí/ to form the adverbial phrase *ibí* "here" and *ibè yẹn* "over there". The place adverb/adverbial may also occur with determiners or demonstratives, as in (b) above to specify location of the action or event. This is done in a sequence where the locative noun appears first *ibè* "there" followed by a determiner or demonstrative *yẹn* "that/over".

3.3 Adverbial Phrase of Frequency

Frequency adverbs "specify the frequency with which an event occurs. They typically answer the question *how often?*" Berk (1999:195). Saah (2004:62) notes that "frequency adverbs modify the meaning of the verb by indicating the number of times the action took place or will take place or has taken place." There are such adverbs in Yorùbá that specify the number of times an event occurs. They are:

ìgbà gbogbo	Always
lẹ̀ékòòkan	Occasionally/Sometimes
lẹ̀ekan	Once
ṣòwón	Rarely
rára	Never
léraléra	Frequently

Some items in the list are exemplified below in (4) a-b:

- (a) **Gbogbo ìgbà** “always”
 Mo máa ní jẹ èwà ní **gbogbo ìgbà**
 1SG will PROG. eat-HAB beans at-PREP every time
 ‘I do eat beans always’
- (b) **Lẹ̀ékòòkan** “occasionally”
 Mo máa ní jẹ èwà **lẹ̀ékòòkan**
 1SG will PROG. eat beans occasionally
 ‘I do eat beans sometimes’
- Adv"
 Adv'
 Adv°
lẹ̀ékòòkan

Figure 3.3: X-Bar Schema for Bare Adverb Phrase

In the examples above, “**gbogbo ìgbà**” (always) and “**lẹ̀ékòòkan**” (occasionally) tell us how often the actions in the sentences took place. They indicate how frequent the actions occur. Interestingly, they both appear predicatively, after the V/VP. They also post-modified the verbs they modified “**jẹ**” (eat). However, they can as well pre-modify the verbs when they are focused or topicalised, thereby yielding sentences (5) like:

- a. (i) **Gbogbo-ìgbà** ni mo máa ní jẹ èwà
 Every-time FOC. 1SG will PROG. eat beans
 ‘I do eat beans always’
- b. (ii) **Lẹ̀ékòòkan** ni mo máa ní jẹ èwà
 Occasionally FOC. 1SG will PROG. eat beans
 ‘I do eat beans occasionally’

Other examples of frequency adverbs in Yorùbá are:

- (a) Àràárò every morning
 (b) Ọ̀sòòsán every afternoon
 (c) Alaalé every evening
 (d) Ojoojumó everyday/daily
 (e) Ọ̀sòòsẹ every week/weekly
 (f) Oṣoosù every month/monthly
 (g) Odoṣodún every year/yearly

Morphologically, Yorùbá frequency adverbs are not formed by attaching any suffix to a noun as it is the case in English. Nabaarese (2017:76) notes that in English, “nouns referring to time units can often be transformed into adverbs of frequency by adding an {-ly} suffix...” Examples of such adverbs include; *hourly, daily, weekly, yearly* etc. However, in Yorùbá nouns that refer to specific

time frame or unit may be combined with another noun (NP) to express frequency. In this case, a change in the grammatical category triggers a change in word form, with a different root substituting for the normal one. This is the case, suppletion takes place between the two words to yield the new NP.e.g *oṣù* (month) + *oṣù* (month) = *Oṣooṣù* (every month/monthly). Let us consider the following sentences in (6) a-b:

(a) *Àràárò* “every morning”

Àràárò ni mo máa ń fọ ẹnu
 Every morning FOC. 1SG will PROG. wash mouth
 “I do brush my teeth every morning”

(b) *Oṣooṣù* “every month/monthly”

Oṣooṣù ni mo máa ń kó àjọ
 Monthly FOC. 1SG will PROG. pack contribution
 “I withdraw my contributions every month”

In both sentences above, “*àràárò*” (every morning) and “*oṣooṣù*” (every month/monthly) pre-modified the Vs “*fọ*” (wash) and “*kó*” (pack) respectively. Without altering the meaning and senses in the sentences, they can as well post-modify the Vs.

3.4 Adverbial Phrase of Manner

According to Givón (2001:88) manner adverbs typically modify or add to the meaning of the verb. The semantic range of such modification is wide and heterogeneous, depending on the specific meaning of the verb. Saah and Agbedor (2004:203) also describe manner adverbs as adverbs which “typically describe the way in which an action or event took place or was executed.” Yorùbá manner adverbs may occur in various forms. They may occur in single-word form, they may be reduplicated and be realised in the form of ideophones.

3.4.1 Single-word Manner Adverbs

Yorùbá manner adverbs may be realised as single-words. These adverbs are typically one-syllable or two-syllable words which are not marked morphologically for any class or tense. Examples of such adverbs include; *fò* (so fair in complexion), *gan* (so, really), *kù* (so heavily) etc. We consider the following examples in (6) a-c:

(a) *Ọmọ náà pón fò*
 Child that-DET red (complexion) fair
 ‘The child is so fair’

(b) *Ọbẹ náà ta gan*
 Soup that-DET hot much
 ‘The soup is too pepperish’

Figure 3.4: X-bar Schema Showing Single Manner Adverb Phrase

(c) *Ọjò sọ ilẹ kù*
 Rain hit ground heavily
 ‘Rain fell so heavily’

‘Rain fell so heavily’

Figure 3.5: X-Bar Schematic Diagram of Adjunct in Manner Adverb Phrase

The adverbs *fò* (so fair), *gan* (so pepperish), and *kù* (so heavily) are all single-word adverbs that modify the verbs *pón* (red), *ta* (hot) and *sò* (hit) respectively. These adverbs describe their respective verbs by providing us information about the activity of the verbs. For example, the adverb *fò* (so fair) describes how fair in complexion the child is in (a). *gan* (so pepperish) also describes how hot the soup is as a result of too much pepper in (b). *kù* (so heavily) gives us information about how heavy the rain fell in (c). We also note that all these adverbs post-modified the verbs in the sentences.

3.4.2 Reduplicated Adverbs in Yorùbá

Various discussions in the literature clearly point to the fact that adverbs can be formed through different processes. These processes may include derivational, inflectional, lexical, phrasal, clausal and in some cases through the combination of some of these processes. They however note that languages vary in terms of how these processes operate. Looking at the morphology of Yorùbá adverbs as lexical items, it is observed that unlike the categories of noun and verb, majority of the adverbs cannot be derived through any morphological process in Yorùbá language other than reduplication. The language operates mainly the morphological processes of affixation, reduplication, and compounding. However, there are still many adverbs of time/manner that are derived through the process of reduplication. They are divisible into two equal parts, each part constituting an independent member of a class but within the same class of adverb. Several items do not seem to make sense when any part of the reduplicated form is removed from the base. Adéwólé (1999:42) refers to these two varieties of adverbs respectively as compositional and non-compositional adverbs. In other words, these could also be referred to as partial morpheme reduplication and full morpheme reduplication (Zuniga and Diaz-Fernandez, 2014).

It will be demonstrated that reduplication in Yorùbá could either be partial or total while each of these two broad categories could be further divided into other subcategories. These are the most straightforward and possibly the most productive cases of reduplication in Yorùbá. Fólárìn (1987) and Beck (2008) refer to some of the data in this category as “full morpheme reduplication” because the copying process involves the whole stem. Examples, among others, are:

7. Bámú + bamu = bàmúbámú ‘totally’
- Ráú + ráú = ráúráú ‘completely’
- Pátá + pátá = pátápátá ‘entirely’
- Yángá + yángá = yángáyángá ‘entirely’
- Kíá + kíá = kíákíá ‘quickly’
- Wéré + wéré = wéréwéré ‘immediately’

These forms are also known as ideophones (Awóyalé, 1974). Usually they have a CVCV-CVCV or CVV-CVV syllable structure but the tonal melody is same for each part, as in example (8) below:

- i. Bàmúbámú ‘totally’
- ii. Ráúráú ‘completely’

- | | | |
|------|------------|------------|
| iii. | Pátápátá | ‘entirely’ |
| iv. | Kíákíá | ‘quickly’ |
| v. | Yángáyángá | ‘entirely’ |

Again, there are other adverbs in this class which has equal number of syllables on either side of the CVCV-CVCV structure but the tonal melody is different for each part. Examples are in (9) below:

- | | | |
|------|------------|----------------------------|
| i) | Réderède | ‘disorderly’ |
| ii) | Rudurudu | ‘disorderly’ |
| iii) | Jálajàla | ‘confusingly’ |
| iv) | Básubàṣu | ‘in a disorganized manner’ |
| v) | Yánnayànnà | ‘in a chaotic manner’ |

In addition, the analysis below shows how some of the adverbs itemized above function in relation to other categories in Yorùbá sentences. Examples:

10. i). **bámúbámú** ‘totally’
 Ṣolá mu ẹmu yó **bámúbámú**
 Ṣolá-N drink-PST palmwine full totally
 ‘Sola was totally drunk of palmwine’
- ii). **ráúrúú** ‘completely’
 Owó nàà ti pòórà **ráúrúú**
 Money the-DET has disappear completely
 ‘The money is completely lost’
- iii). **pátápátá** ‘entirely’
 Owó óunjẹ mí ti tán **pátápátá**
 Money food my-POSS has finish entirely
 ‘My feeding money is entirely finished’
- iv). **kíákíá** ‘quickly’
 Jẹ ká lọ **kíákíá**
 Let shall-we go quickly
 ‘Let us go quickly’
- v). **yángáyángá** ‘entirely’
 Ó fọ igbá nàà **yángáyángá**
 S/he break calabash the entirely
 ‘He broke the calabash entirely’

CONCLUSION

This work sought to analyse Yorùbá phrases, with a view to examine and describe the adverbial phrase structure of Yorùbá, in terms of the different syntactic interactions, which the least composite units called phrases, like the noun and verb phrases undergo, to form sentences, using the X-bar model. An adverbial phrase (also known as an adverb phrase) is a group of words that functions as an adverb in a sentence. That is, it modifies a verb, adjective, adverb, clause, or the sentence as a whole. Adverb as an open word-class is heterogeneous in nature because it allows other categories such as noun phrase and prepositional phrase to function in the same slot as adverbs. Adverbs typically modify or add to, the meaning of the verb, adjective, adverb, clause, or the sentence as a whole. The

semantic range of such modification is wide and heterogeneous, depending on the specific meaning of the word modified.

REFERENCES

- Adesola, O. (2010). The non-agreeing subject resumptive pronoun in Yoruba. In Aboh, Enoch and James Essegbey (eds.), *Topics in Kwa syntax*. London: Springer, 65–89.
- Adéwole, L. O. (1990). Some Aspects of Negation in Yorùbá. *AAP (Köln)*, 28, 75-100.
- Adéwole, L. O. (1999). Negation in Ifẹ̀: A Yorùbá dialect. *Journal of Asian and African Studies* 58, 397-403.
- Agbedo, C.U. (2000). *General Linguistics: An Introductory Reader*. Nsukka: ACE Resources Consult.
- Agbedo, C. U. (2009). *Language and Mind: A New Direction in Psycholinguistics*. Nsukka: Ark Kumbiz Services.
- Beck, D. (2008). Ideophones, Adverbs, and Predicate Qualification in Upper Necaxa Totonac. *International Journal of American Linguistics* 74 (1) 1-46.
- Berk, L. M. (1999). *English Syntax*: Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Chomsky, N. (1988) *Language and problems of Knowledge*. The Nicaragua Lectures. Cambridge Mass: MIT Press.
- Folarin, A. (1987). ‘Lexical Phonology of Yoruba Nouns and Verbs’. University of Kansas, Ph.D Dissertation.
- Givón, T. (2001). *Syntax. Vol. 1*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins. Kirkpatrick, B. (2007). *Correct English*. New Lanark. Greddes and Grosset
- Nabaarese, J. A. (2017). A study of Kasem adverbs and adverbials. M.Phil. (Linguistics) thesis. University of Ghana. <http://ugspace.ug.edu.gh>
- Radford, A. (1988). *Transformational grammar: A first course*. Cambridge: Cambridge university press.
- Saah, Kofi K. 2004. A Survey of Akan Adverbs and Adverbials. *Journal of West African Languages* XXX 1 (2), 47-74.
- Shopen, Timothy. (ed.). 2007. *Language Typology and Syntactic Description (2ed.): Clause Structure*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Zuniga, U. & Diaz-Fernandez, C. (2014). Reduplication in Mapuzungun: Form and function. Vort, H.V. and Gomez, G.G. (Eds). *Reduplication in Indigenous Languages of South America*. Boston: Brill.